

1 Multivariate allergen-specific profiling of
2 serum antibodies from patients with peanut
3 allergy
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21 **Supplementary materials and methods**

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23 *Study cohort, ethics and informed consent*

24 The study was performed on a Swiss cohort of 101 males and females peanut-allergic
25 patients. Both adults and children were included and the age of the study subjects ranged
26 from 3 to 69 years. All patients had a conclusive clinical case history of peanut allergy and
27 were sensitised to peanut allergens verified by positive skin prick test (wheal greater than 3
28 mm) and allergen-specific IgE testing (IgE greater than 0.35 kilo units of allergen per litre,
29 kUA/L). Exclusion criteria were patients with age <3 years and patients suffering from any
30 disease where blood withdrawals might impact on the patient's health status. Sampling of
31 blood was performed at the University Hospital of Zurich and at the University Children's
32 Hospital Zurich. Samples were collected between June 2016 and March 2020. Ethical approval
33 from the Cantonal Ethics Committee of Zurich was granted in May 2016 (BASEC no. 2016-
34 00348). The study was classified according to the Human Research Act as a HRO trial of
35 category A. All study subjects provided a written informed consent to blood collection and to
36 the use, analysis, and publication of the generated data.

37 *Determination of allergen-specific IgE and IgG4 antibodies by ImmunoCAP*

38 The concentration of IgE against Ara h 1 (f422), Ara h 2 (f423), Ara h 3 (f424), Ara h 6 (f447),
39 Ara h 8 (f352), Ara h 9 (f427) and peanut allergen extract (f13) were determined in serum
40 using the ImmunoCAP system (ThermoFisher Scientific, Phadia, Waltham, US-MA) according
41 to the manufacturer's instructions. The cut-off for a positive test result was 0.35 kUA/L.
42 Similarly, the concentration of IgG4 against Ara h 2 (f423), Ara h 6 (f447), and peanut allergen
43 extract (f13) were determined in serum using ImmunoCAP.

44 *Detection of allergen-specific IgG by ELISA*

45 IgG antibodies against Ara h 1, Ara h 2, Ara h 3, Ara h 6, Ara h 8 and PE were determined using
46 an in-house developed ELISA method. Maxisorp 96 well ELISA plates were coated overnight
47 with 1 µg/ml purified natural Ara h 1 (NA-AH1-1), Ara h 2 (NA-AH2-1), Ara h 3 (NA-AH3-1), Ara
48 h 6 (NA-AH6-1), recombinant Ara h 8 (RE-AH8-1) and peanut allergen extract (LTN-AHRE-1) in
49 carbonate buffer at pH 9.6. All allergens were purchased from INDOOR Biotechnologies Ltd.
50 (Cardiff, UK). Coated plates were blocked one hour with 5% skimmed milk in phosphate-

51 buffered saline (PBS) with 0.05% polysorbate (PBST) and then incubated two hours with serial
52 dilutions of patient serum in PBST with 1% milk. Biotinylated mouse anti-human IgG (BD
53 Biosciences, #555785; Franklin Lakes, US-NJ) was used as detection antibody (one hour).
54 Subsequent 30 minute incubation of streptavidin-conjugated horse-radish peroxidase
55 (Streptavidin-HRP; BioLegend, #405210; San Diego, US-CA) followed by incubation with
56 tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) substrate allowed the assay development. The colorimetric
57 enzyme reaction was stopped with 2N H₂SO₄ and the absorbance read at 450 nm using ELx808
58 microplate reader from BioTek (Luzern, CH). Antibody end-point titre was defined as last
59 positive titre higher than three standard deviations above the mean optical density of PBST
60 without serum samples. Since all samples were diluted 200-fold or more, an end-point titre
61 of 100 was assigned to patients with negative sera at 200-fold dilution.

62 *Statistical analysis*

63 Statistical analysis was performed with R Studio (v4.1.0) and GraphPad Prism (v8.0.0). The
64 differences between age groups were calculated using one-way ANOVA. The differences
65 between independent groups were calculated using non-parametric, two-tailed Mann-
66 Whitney U tests. IgE concentrations and IgG titres are indicated as median and geometric
67 mean with 95% confidential intervals respectively. The linear association between different
68 allergen-specific IgE concentrations was measured by Pearson's correlation coefficient (r).
69 Age and gender associations were calculated using a two-way ANOVA and p-values were
70 multiple testing corrected using Benjamini and Hochberg False Discovery Rate. Significant
71 differences were annotated with asterisks: p<0.05: *; p<0.01: **; p<0.001: ***.